

COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT IN IMPLEMENTING THE PERMATA POMAA STUNTING HANDLING MODEL BASED ON DIGITAL EDUCATION AND GITOK

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Abstract

The Community Empowerment Program in the Implementation of the Permata Pomaa Stunting Handling Model based on Digital Education and the Development of GITOK (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) was carried out in Simpang Lhee Village, West Langsa District, where the target partners involved in this activity were the target partners of the Non-Productive community group, namely Posyandu cadres and the target partners of the Productive community group, namely the Awaina UMKM This village was recorded as having 341 families at risk of stunting caused by the community's low understanding of nutrition, the habit of giving low-nutrition foods such as instant noodles and used cooking oil, and economic factors that limit access to healthy food. Irregular children's eating patterns and the habit of letting children have difficulty eating without solutions have worsened this situation, as well as the weak economy of the community in the village, where Simpang Lhee Village, West Langsa District is also included in the area with the extreme poverty line. Awaina UMKM has been involved in the production of shrimp paste, salted fish. However, so far the production produced by Awaina UMKM is very limited and its marketing is only in the local area of Langsa City. As a solution, this program presents a technological and empowering approach to Stunting Management PERMATA POMAA based on Digital Education through the development of the PERMATA POMAA & GITOK digital education application. This application provides information regarding the Supplementary Food Menu for children, how to regulate diets, baby massage and Tuina massage to increase appetite. In addition, the program also encourages the use of home gardens as hydroponic-based nutritional gardens to provide affordable and independent healthy food ingredients. The program implementation includes stages of socialization, training, technology application, mentoring, and periodic evaluation.

Keywords: *Permata Pomaa; Education; Digital; Gitok; Stunting*

INTRODUCTION

The nutritional status of children under five is an important health indicator because this age group is vulnerable to nutritional problems and disease. Inadequate nutritional intake during the first five years can result in irreversible growth and developmental disorders, including physical, mental, and brain disorders. Malnutrition in children remains a significant problem in Indonesia, with symptoms such as low birth weight, wasting, and stunting. Stunting is a chronic condition of malnutrition that, in the long term, can lead to stunted growth, decreased cognitive and mental abilities, susceptibility to disease, low economic productivity, and poor reproductive quality. Indonesia still ranks fifth and fourth highest in the world in terms of wasting and stunting rates. Based on the results of the Indonesian Nutrition Survey (SSGI), it shows that the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia in 2024 is 19.8%. Meanwhile, the prevalence of stunting in Aceh in 2024 is 28.6%. Where there is a decrease in stunting rates compared

to 2023. Despite the decline, Aceh is still included in the top five provinces with the highest stunting rates in Indonesia. Meanwhile, based on data from the Langsa City Health Profile in West Langsa District, there are 9,216 cases of families at risk of stunting, and based on data from Simpang Lhee village in 2023, there are 341 cases of stunting risk. One of the causes of stunting in children is dietary intake. Children who consume a diverse diet have better nutritional status. However, this presents a challenge for children with eating difficulties. Children with eating difficulties are characterized by a loss of appetite and inadequate complementary food intake, resulting in inadequate intake of quality food and essential nutrients, which contributes to stunting. Stunting management has been carried out by health workers and community health centers, but has not been able to reduce the incidence of stunting significantly, so there needs to be a touch from the world of education and universities in terms of modifying stunting management that is right on target by empowering the community in improving nutritional status for appropriate stunting management.

This is supported by the results of community service from Sutrisna et al. (2024) showed an increase in the average knowledge of participants before and after counseling, and an increase in the weight and height of toddlers after the Permata Pomaa community service activity. The Permata Pomaa stunting management model includes providing supplementary food, regulating diet, infant massage, and Tuina massage to increase children's appetite. This is based on the research results of Maulida et al. (2024). shows that there is an effect of giving Tuina Massage on increasing the weight of stunted toddlers and there is an effect of giving Tuina Massage on increasing the height of stunted toddlers. Therefore, the purpose of community service carried out through community empowerment by the Student Executive Board aims to empower the community in implementing the PERTAMA POMAA stunting management model based on Digital Education and GITOK (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) Development in Simpang Lhee Village, Langsa City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Stunting as a Public Health Problem

Stunting is a condition of growth failure in toddlers due to chronic malnutrition that persists from pregnancy through the first two years of life. This condition is characterized by height-for-age below the WHO standard deviation and has long-term impacts on cognitive development, learning capacity, economic productivity, and the risk of degenerative diseases in adulthood (UNICEF, 2020). In Indonesia, stunting remains a national priority health issue. According to the 2024 Indonesian Nutritional Status Survey (SSGI), the national prevalence of stunting reached 19.8%, while Aceh Province remains among the provinces with the highest stunting rate, at 28.6% (Ministry of Health, 2025). This high prevalence indicates that stunting management cannot rely solely on curative interventions but requires a community-based promotive and preventive approach.

2. Factors Causing Stunting and Nutritional Parenting Patterns

Stunting is influenced by various multidimensional factors, including inadequate nutritional intake, irregular eating patterns, recurrent infectious diseases, socioeconomic conditions, and low family knowledge about child nutrition (UNICEF, 2020). Children with eating difficulties tend to have insufficient energy and nutrient intake, putting them at risk of linear growth disorders. Research shows that food diversity and proper dietary management play a crucial role in improving the nutritional status of toddlers. However, economic constraints and the habit of consuming low-nutrient foods like instant noodles and used cooking oil remain major challenges in communities at risk of stunting (Ministry of Health, 2025).

3. PERMATA POMAA Stunting Management Model

The PERMATA POMAA (Supplementary Food, Dietary Management, and Child Massage) model is an innovative approach that integrates nutritional interventions and non-pharmacological stimulation to improve toddler appetite and growth. A study by Maulida et al. (2024) shows that the application of Tui Na massage in the PERMATA POMAA model has a significant effect on increasing the weight and height of stunted toddlers. In addition, community service carried out by Sutrisna et al. (2024) demonstrated that the PERMATA POMAA model can improve maternal knowledge, dietary compliance, and toddler nutritional status. This confirms the strategic role of family-based interventions and integrated health post (Posyandu) cadres in preventing and managing stunting.

4. The Role of Digital Education in Stunting Prevention

The use of digital technology in public health is increasingly emerging as an effective, accessible, and sustainable educational tool. Digital education enables the interactive delivery of health information through videos,

infographics, and smartphone-based applications, thereby increasing public understanding and changing behavior. In the context of stunting, digital education plays a role in improving nutritional literacy, understanding of complementary feeding (MP-ASI), and parenting skills. The PERMATA POMAA educational app is an effective support tool for strengthening community-based interventions, particularly in areas with limited access to conventional education.

5. GITOK (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) as a Solution for Nutritional Security

The use of hydroponic-based nutrition gardens (GITOK) is an innovative strategy to increase the availability of healthy food at the household level. Hydroponic systems enable independent, land-efficient, and sustainable production of nutritious vegetables. This approach aligns with community empowerment efforts to improve family food security and reduce dependence on processed foods. The integration of GITOK with the stunting management program strengthens access to nutritious food while increasing community economic independence through the development of local food-based MSMEs.

6. Community Empowerment and the Role of Cadres and MSMEs

Community empowerment is key to the success of a sustainable stunting prevention program. Integrated service post (Posyandu) cadres act as agents of change in improving family knowledge and skills, while MSMEs contribute to the development of nutritious local food and improving family economic well-being. A collaborative approach between health workers, universities, village governments, cadres, and MSMEs has proven to be effective in strengthening the effectiveness of stunting management programs and encouraging their sustainability at the village level.

7. Research Gap

Although various stunting management programs have been implemented, most still focus on conventional nutrition interventions and have not been integrated with digital education and community economic empowerment. Furthermore, the use of hydroponic technology as a source of family nutrition in stunting programs remains limited. Therefore, the implementation of the PERMATA POMAA model, based on digital education and the development of GITOK, is expected to provide a comprehensive solution to address this gap.

METHOD

This activity was carried out in Simpang Lhee Village, West Langsa District, Langsa City from September to December 2025, this activity involved 20 Bumi Persada University students consisting of the Nursing Study Program, Midwifery Study Program, Medical Informatics Study Program, Management Study Program.

The following are the stages of implementation of Community Empowerment activities in the Implementation of the Permata Pomaa stunting management model based on digital education and Gitok (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) Development, including the following:

a. Preparation stages

The preparation stage begins with obtaining permits for the implementation of activities at the Educational Institution and the location of the activity, namely Simpang Lhee Village. After obtaining the permit, data collection of activity participants is carried out with the help of Posyandu cadres and village midwives. Next, preparation of the service team is carried out through a committee meeting to divide tasks and prepare activity equipment such as banners, powerpoints, leaflets, participant souvenirs and equipment loans (LCD and projector screens).

b. Implementation Stages

1) Socialization

The activity begins with an initial meeting with partners, a presentation or socialization to provide information to the community so that mothers of stunted toddlers are willing to participate in the community empowerment program in the implementation of the PERMATA POMAA stunting management model based on digital education and the development of community nutrition gardens, namely providing supplementary food based on local ingredients available in the community, regulating toddler diets, baby massage for toddler growth and development and Tui Na Massage to increase the appetite of stunted toddlers and nutrition from family organic plants. The activity will be held at the Simpang Lhee Village Hall attended by mothers who have stunted toddlers. The material presented includes an introduction to providing supplementary food based on local ingredients, such as the use of

Moringa leaves to increase children's nutritional intake, menu variations for toddlers along with how to process and serve them, as well as an introduction to baby massage and Tui Na massage techniques starting from their benefits, movements used, to the link between infant nutritional status and stunting incidents. The method used in this activity is an interactive lecture with a question and answer session, supported by PowerPoint presentation media. The activity was officially opened by representatives from the West Langsa Health Center, Simpang Lhee Village officials, representatives of Bumi Persada University, and the community service implementation team. Before the material is delivered, participants will take a pre-test for approximately 15 minutes using a questionnaire. The material will then be delivered by the community service team, followed by a question-and-answer session, and concluded with a post-test to gauge participant understanding.

2) Training

This activity was also carried out by providing training to Posyandu cadres including baby massage to improve child growth and development, Tui Na massage to increase appetite, and Oxytocin massage to increase breast milk production. Participants in this activity were Posyandu cadres and mothers with stunted toddlers, who were trained directly to perform baby massage techniques, Tui Na massage and oxytocin massage. In this activity, mothers were given a baby massage module as a guide. Next, they were given training in making supplementary foods from local ingredients that are rich in nutrition, one of which is by utilizing Moringa leaves, while learning how to serve them. In addition, training was also provided to the Awaina MSME Group, including training in the production of other MSME products such as moon fish crackers, Moringa leaf bhoi, rebon shrimp crackers, fish floss, MSME management training, packaging training, and marketing training.

3) Application of technology

The application of technology in the form of the PERMATA POMAA Educational Application and KEBUN GITOK is part of an educational activity aimed at increasing public understanding, especially families of stunted toddlers, regarding digital-based stunting prevention and management and the utilization of local resources. This activity was carried out through training and simulations for Posyandu cadres and mothers of toddlers. In the simulation, participants were invited to try various application features. Video tutorials on making, interactive infographics on balanced nutrition, a guide to baby massage steps, tips and planting schedules for the Nutrition Garden.

4) Mentoring

Providing assistance to Posyandu cadres and mothers with stunted toddlers in infant massage, Tui Na massage, and oxytocin massage, preparing supplementary food from local foods, and managing children's diets. In addition, providing assistance to the Awaina MSME group in production, MSME management, and marketing.

5) Evaluation

Evaluation of the outreach activities was conducted through a direct question and answer session with participants and questionnaires to measure their knowledge gains. Furthermore, the evaluation included an assessment of the program's structure, the presentation of materials by the speakers, and participant responses during the event. Additional evaluations included a post-test and observations of the skills of cadres and mothers of toddlers in performing infant massage and Tui Na massage, as well as anthropometric measurements of stunted toddlers. This evaluation phase also examined packaged processed food products and dried fish products, particularly in terms of their marketing potential.

c. Evaluation stages and program sustainability

Program evaluation is conducted through routine monthly monitoring through cadre reports and field observations, knowledge and behavior surveys before and after digital education, periodic measurement of children's nutritional status (weight/age, height/age), assessment of the success of the GITOK garden through household production and consumption indicators. The sustainability of the program is designed through cadre training, handing over the Permata Pomaa and Gitok applications to villages as archives and educational tools, independent management of hydroponic nutrition gardens by mothers' groups or PKK, integration of the program into routine Posyandu activities and village government work plans (RKDes).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PM-BEM Impacts Community Empowerment in the Implementation of the Permata Pomaa Stunting Handling Model Based on Digital Education and Gitok Development (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) in Simpang Lhee

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Village, Langsa City, implemented for 4 (four) months from September to December 2025 in 2 Partner groups, namely the economically unproductive community group, namely Health Cadres and the economically productive community, namely the Awaina MSME in Simpang Lhee Village, West Langsa District, Langsa City, with the scope of the first problem being the social aspect of society and the scope of the second problem being the management aspect. Community Service Team Coming from three different areas of expertise , namely Health, Computer Technology, and Management , they contributed to the PM-BEM Program activities . The results of the PM-BEM activities that have been implemented:

Table 3. Results of PM BEM Community Empowerment Activities

ACTIVITY		PIC	DAY/DATE IMPLEMENTATION	PLACE	ACTIVITY RESULTS/ OUTPUT AND OUTCAME
1	Impactful Student Executive Board Socialization	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Thursday, September 18, 2025	Bumi Persada University	Submit a notification letter to the Chancellor, Dean and Head of Study Program regarding students involved in BEM Berdampak activities.
2	Provision for students who participate in BEM Berdampak activities	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Friday, September 19, 2025	Bumi Persada University	Providing Provisions to Students Who Participate in Impactful BEM Activities
3	Initial observations stage I to Partner Village	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Saturday, September 20, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Exploration to the village and submission of a permit letter to the Geusyk of Simpang Lhee Village, West Langsa to carry out student activities of the BEM Berdampak
4	Handover of Impact Bem students	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb and Team	Tuesday, September 23, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Handover of PM Bem Berdampak students and Program Socialization
5	Practical Training on Making Local Food with Nutritional Value	Husna Maulida, SST., and team	Saturday, September 27, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Highly nutritious local foods such as moon fish crackers and moon fish nuggets
6	Hydroponic Nutrition Technology Training	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Tuesday, October 7, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	<p>a. Partner health cadres and groups of mothers of stunted toddlers have been given training in hydroponic nutrition technology in Simpang Lhee Village.</p> <p>b. Improvement of skills in making hydroponic nutritional plants before and after training.</p>
7	Community Empowerment in Hydroponic Nutrition Production	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Saturday, October 11, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	The skills improvement of partner Health Cadres and groups of mothers of stunted toddlers have been given empowerment on how to make Hydroponic Nutrition Production so that the nutritional value of toddlers is

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					fulfilled through healthy plants and green vegetables.
8	Tui na Massage and Oxytocin Massage Training for Posyandu cadres	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Sunday, October 12, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	<p>a. Partner Health Cadres have received Child Massage and Tui Na Massage Training in Simpang Lhee Village</p> <p>b. Increased knowledge about the importance of Oxytocin Massage in children and Tui Na Massage for toddler growth and appetite.</p>
9	Simpang Lhee Village	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Tuesday, October 14, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Partner Health Cadres can independently practice massage on children and Tui Na massage for toddler growth and appetite, so that it can be empowered in the community and mothers of toddlers in preventing stunting.
10	Community Empowerment of Oxytocin Massage Practice for Health Cadres in Simpang Lhee Village	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Wednesday, October 15, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Partner Health Cadres can independently practice Oxytocin Massage on breastfeeding mothers to facilitate breast milk production, so that it can be used by breastfeeding mothers.
11	Advanced Practical Training in Making Local Food with Nutritional Value	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Friday, October 17, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	<p>a. Improving the knowledge and skills of partner health cadres in making nutritious local food .</p> <p>b. Highly nutritious local foods such as Bhoi Moringa leaves and mussel nuggets</p>
12	Community Empowerment Local Food Making Practices	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Saturday, October 18, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	<p>a. Partner health cadres and MSME groups gain understanding and knowledge about making locally based food supplements with high nutritional value.</p> <p>b. Improving the skills of partner health cadres and MSME groups in local food production .</p>
13	Awaina MSME Product Production Training	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Sunday, October 19, 2024	Simpang Lhee Village	Produce more hygienic and diverse products by using a grinding machine
14	Awaina Large-Scale MSME Product	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih,	Wednesday, October 22, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	<p>a. Increase production per 500 pieces/day for marketing</p> <p>b. There are various local food</p>

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	Production Training	ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM			products ready to be marketed.
15	Community Empowerment in the Production of Awaina MSME Products	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Friday, October 24, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. MSMEs produce an increasing number of products to be marketed b. MSMEs produce a variety of food products from local ingredients
16	Community Empowerment in the Production of Moonfish Crackers and Reborn Shrimp Crackers	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Sunday, October 26, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Increased production of Awaina MSMEs per day by 100 pieces
17	Awaina MSME Management Training	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Tuesday, October 28, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. SOP for sanitation and hygiene management, and Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) related to food safety b. Bookkeeping system using application
18	Empowering Awaina MSMEs in Marketing Management	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Saturday, November 1, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Improving digital bookkeeping systems
19	Packaging and marketing training for Awaina MSME products in Simpang Lhee village	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Wednesday, November 5, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. The Awaina MSME Group gained understanding and knowledge about how to market their products. b. MSME products can be marketed widely and with attractive packaging.
20	Community Empowerment in Attractive Packaging of MSME Products	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Saturday, November 8, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. MSME skills in attractive packaging to revive MSMEs b. More skilled MSMEs and more attractive product packaging
21	Empowerment of Awaina MSME Community in Product Labeling	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Sunday, November 9, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. Attractive labeling of Awaina UMKM b. MSME products are economically valuable and attractive.
22	Socialization of Digital Education Information Technology	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Monday, November 10, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Digital Educational Information Technology at Integrated Health Posts

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23	Community Empowerment in the Use of Digital Educational Information Technology	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Tuesday, November 11, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	Utilization of Digital Educational Information Technology at Integrated Health Posts (Posyandu)
24	Community Empowerment in Marketing Awaina MSME Products	Husna Maulida, SST., M.Keb, Eka Utami Ningsih, ST., MT and Ismuhadi, MSM	Thursday, November 13, 2025	Simpang Lhee Village	a. Improving MSME skills in marketing Awaina products b. Wider marketing c. Increasing MSME income

This program improves the skills of cadre partners and mothers of toddlers in making nutritious food for children, improving skills in making hydroponic nutritional plants so that toddlers' nutritional value is met through healthy green vegetables, increasing knowledge and skills in performing massage on children, tuina massage to increase appetite, oxytocin massage to increase breast milk production, in addition to increasing the knowledge and skills of MSME cadres in producing more hygienic MSME products, increasing MSME product production, improving digital bookkeeping systems, more attractive MSME product packaging and increasing wider marketing. This activity is also supported by the official support of the village government for the PERMATA POMAA program and including the program in the village work agenda as part of efforts to accelerate prevention and reduce the risk of stunting and family economic empowerment. the availability of internet and devices such as smartphones that enable cadres and the community to learn about the prevention and handling of stunting Permata Pomaa and Gitok through the Educational application "PERMATA POMAA & KEBUN GITOK" which contains information about regulating diet, MP-ASI, traditional massage therapy (Baby massage, Tui Na Massage, Oxytocin Massage), and information about the benefits of hydroponic plants and family medicinal plants independently, the availability of internet and devices such as smartphones that enable cadres and the community to learn about the prevention and handling of stunting Permata Pomaa and Gitok through the Educational application "PERMATA POMAA & KEBUN GITOK" which contains information about regulating diet, MP-ASI, traditional massage therapy (Baby massage, Tui Na Massage, Oxytocin Massage), and information about the benefits of hydroponic plants and family medicinal plants independently, and the Availability of local resources in the form of access to clean water, land conditions, so that it is possible to carry out nutritional planting of Hydroponic technology, in addition to the availability of raw materials for making shrimp paste, namely rebon shrimp and moringa leaves, so that it is possible to produce production shrimp paste, crackers and Bhoi moringa leaves in large quantities. However, there are several things that also become obstacles in carrying out this activity, including the availability of local resources in the form of access to clean water, land conditions, so that it is possible to carry out the planting of Hydroponic technology nutrition, in addition to the availability of raw materials for making shrimp paste, namely rebon shrimp and Moringa leaves so that it is possible to produce shrimp paste, crackers and Bhoi Moringa leaves in large quantities, Lack of family motivation and distrust of external programs are also obstacles in this implementation, Lack of public awareness in making home-made food preparations by utilizing local food ingredients, where people still focus only on providing additional food provided by the government. In addition, it is difficult to gather MSME group members on time, this is due to the busyness of MSME members.

CONCLUSION (TNR, 12 BOLD)

Community Empowerment Activities in the implementation of the Permata Pomaa Stunting Handling model based on Digital Education and Gitok Development (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition) carried out in Simpang Lhee Village, Langsa City, can be concluded that this program has great potential to reduce the incidence of stunting in Indonesia, through PERMATA POMAA stunting handling, namely Providing additional food, Dietary regulation, Baby massage and Tui Na massage and based on digital education by increasing public knowledge about child nutrition that is easy and interactive. While GITOK (Hydroponic Technology Nutrition provides innovative solutions for producing fresh vegetables at the household level and increasing the availability of local nutrition. And active participation from partners such as posyandu cadres, MSMEs and the village government itself strengthens the sustainability of this program.

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